

MIRROR, MIRROR: COLLATZ HITS A WALL

KENNETH ROGER HUTCHINGS

ABSTRACT. At each iteration or step, the Short-cut function of the Collatz Conjecture, when applied to all $n_O \in \mathbb{N}_1$, is proved to produce all possible unique parity sequences at that step. Each unique parity sequence is followed by every element of exactly one properly defined, equally partitioned, strictly and totally ordered, infinite sub-set, $I_j \in \mathbb{N}_1$.

Where $q =$ even steps and $p =$ odd steps, if a theoretical lowest infinitely divergent integer, n_L , exists, for which $f^i(n_L) > n_L$ for all $\text{Steps}_{1 \rightarrow \infty}$, it is proved that $[q/p] < [\log_2(3) - 1]$ for all $\text{Steps}_{1 \rightarrow \infty}$. It maybe impossible to directly prove that n_L does or does not exist.

However, the Short-cut function of the Collatz Conjecture is proved to be a pure infinite binomial expansion and, if n_L does exist, there must also exist a “mirror” lowest infinitely convergent integer, $n_M \in \mathbb{N}_1$, whose unique parity sequence is bilaterally symmetrical to that of n_L , with $[q/p] > [1/(\log_2(3) - 1)]$ for all $\text{Steps}_{1 \rightarrow \infty}$. It is proved that n_M cannot exist and therefore n_L cannot exist. Therefore, all $n_O \in \mathbb{N}_1$ are proved to eventually result in $f^i(n_O) < n_O$.

It is also proved there are no terminal loop sequences possible other than the known trivial terminal loop sequence of (1, 2) of period 2 and, for all $n_O \in \mathbb{N}_1$, eventually, $f^i(n_O) = 1$ and the Collatz Conjecture is proved true.

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Honorary authorship to my wife, Nina, who endured many years and countless hours watching me chase this rabbit, ensuring I didn’t spend too much time down the rabbit-hole, listening to me “explain” the “patterns” and generally keeping me sane.

1. THE COLLATZ CONJECTURE AND THEOREM

1.1. The Collatz Conjecture.

The Short-cut function of the Collatz Conjecture has two potential operations or steps. For all positive integers, if integer $n_{(i-1)}$ is even then $n_i = n_{(i-1)}/2$. If integer $n_{(i-1)}$ is odd then $n_i = (3 * n_{(i-1)} + 1)/2$. The conjecture is that, when applied recursively, eventually, all positive starting integers will result in a terminal periodic sequence of (1,2) of period 2.

1.2. The Collatz Theorem.

Theorem 1.1. *The Collatz Conjecture is true.*

The following are the equations, theorems, lemmas and corollaries presented in this paper, in sequence, for complete proof of the Collatz Conjecture.

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|--|----------------|
| (1) Two equations for $f^i(n_O)$ | Subsection 1.3 |
| (2) Identical and Alternating Parity Equivalence Theorem | Section 2 |
| (3) Infinite Binomial Expansion Corollary | Section 3 |
| (4) Mirror Sub-set and Mirror Parity Sequence Corollary | Section 4 |
| (5) $EV > EEV$ Theorem and $EV > 1$ Lemma | Section 5 |
| (6) No Non-trivial Terminal Loop Sequences Theorem | Section 6 |
| (7) $EL \geq \log_2(n_O) + p * EEV$ Theorem | Section 7 |
| (8) No Infinite Divergence Theorem | Section 8 |
| (9) Final Proof of Collatz Theorem | Section 9 |

This paper proves both of the following and, therefore, proves the validity of the Collatz Conjecture for all positive starting integers.

- (1) There exists no terminal periodic sequence other than the known sequence.
- (2) For every $n_O \in \mathbb{N}_1$, there must exist a Step $_i$, where either $f^i(n_O) < n_O$ or $f^i(n_O) = 1$ (or both, where $n_O = 2$).

1.3. Two equations for $f^i(n_O)$. Where $n_O = n_{\text{Original}}$, two equations are provided for $f^i(n_O)$. These equations are used to derive some of the proofs.

1.3.1. Equation derived from the Conventional Short-cut Collatz Function. The Conventional Short-cut Collatz Function:

$$f(n_i) = \begin{cases} \frac{n_{(i-1)}}{2} & \text{if } n_{(i-1)} \pmod{2} \equiv 0 \\ \frac{3n_{(i-1)}+1}{2} & \text{if } n_{(i-1)} \pmod{2} \equiv 1 \end{cases}$$

can be modified to the equivalent function:

$$f(n_i) = \begin{cases} \frac{3^0 n_{(i-1)}}{2^1} + \frac{(2^0-1)}{2^1} & \text{if } n_{(i-1)} \pmod{2} \equiv 0 \\ \frac{3^1 n_{(i-1)}}{2^1} + \frac{(2^1-1)}{2^1} & \text{if } n_{(i-1)} \pmod{2} \equiv 1 \end{cases}$$

which leads to:

$$(1.1) \quad f^i(n_O) = \frac{3^p * n_O}{2^i} + \frac{b}{2^i} = \frac{3^p * n_O + b}{2^i}$$

where:

- (1) i = Total Number of Steps ($i \geq 0$)
- (2) p = Number of odd Parity Steps ($p \geq 0$)
 - Since 3^p is a power of 3, $3^p \pmod{2} \equiv 1$ and it will always be odd
- (3) q = Number of even Parity Steps ($q \geq 0$)

- (4) $b =$ Integer variable to keep, for each iteration, the numerator of the right hand fraction separate. The exact value of b is never required for proof. The relative value between b_1 and b_2 is needed. The limits and parity of b are also required for the proof.

- Function for b

$$f(b_i) = \begin{cases} b_{(i-1)} & \text{if } n_{(i-1)} \pmod{2} \equiv 0 \\ 3 * b_{(i-1)} + 2^{(i-1)} & \text{if } n_{(i-1)} \pmod{2} \equiv 1 \end{cases}$$

- Used in proof of:

- * Identical and Alternating Parity Equivalence Theorem

- If two starting integers, n_1 and n_2 , follow exactly the same parity sequence from Step₁ to Step _{x} , then from Step₁ to after Step _{x} , $b_1 = b_2$.

- If after Step _{x} , $f^i(n_2) \not\equiv f^i(n_1) \pmod{2}$, then $b_1 \neq b_2$ after Step _{$(x+1)$} .

- Parity of b

$$n_O \pmod{2} \equiv b \pmod{2}$$

- If n_O is odd, the first Step is an odd Parity Step, therefore $b = 2^{(1-1)} = 1$ which is odd. All subsequent odd Parity Steps will add a $2^{(i-1)}$ which will be even and b will be odd.

- If n_O is even, the first Step is an even Parity Step so the odd value 1 will not be added. All subsequent odd Parity Steps will add a $2^{(i-1)}$ value which will be even and b will be even.

- Limits of b

$$0 \leq b \leq 3^i - 2^i$$

Where no odd Steps $i = q$ and $b = 0$

Where all odd Steps $i = p$ and $b = 3^i - 2^i$

- Limits of $\frac{b}{2^{i * \log_2(3)}} = \frac{b}{3^i} = B$: (Note $\frac{b}{3^i} = \frac{b}{3^p}$ for constant odd Steps)

$$(1.2) \quad B = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{3} \leq B < 1 \quad \therefore 0 < B < 1 & \text{if } n_O \pmod{2} \equiv 1 \\ 0 \leq B < 1 \quad \therefore 0 \leq B < 1 & \text{if } n_O \pmod{2} \equiv 0 \end{cases}$$

- Used in proof of:

- * $EV > EEV$ Theorem

- * $EL \geq \log_2(n_O) + p * EEV$ Theorem.

1.3.2. Simple Sum Equation.

$$(1.3) \quad f^i(n_O) = n_O + w \quad \text{where } w \in \mathbb{Z}$$

If $w = 0$ then $f^i(n_O) = n_O$ (Any Terminal Loop)

If $w < 0$ then $f^i(n_O) < n_O$

If $w > 0$ then $f^i(n_O) > n_O$

2. IDENTICAL AND ALTERNATING PARITY EQUIVALENCE THEOREM

Theorem 2.1. *Recursively applying the Short-cut Collatz function to all elements of any properly defined, strictly and totally ordered, finite sub-set $I_j \in \mathbb{N}_1$, where:*

$$\begin{aligned} x &\in \mathbb{N}_0 \\ y &\in \mathbb{N}_0 \\ I_j &\in \{I_1, I_2, I_3, \dots, I_{(2^x)}\} \\ I_j &= \{n_1, n_2, n_3, \dots, n_{(2^y)} \text{ where } n_1 < n_2 < n_3 < \dots < n_{(2^y)}\} \\ I_j &= \{n \mid n = j + m * 2^x \text{ for all } m \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, 2^y - 1\}\} \\ |I_j| &= 2^y \end{aligned}$$

will result in exactly identical parity sequences, for all $n_O \in I_j$, up to and including Step_x. Immediately after Step_x, the parity of $f^x(n_O)$, for each sequential element of sub-set I_j , will alternate.

By extension, prior to every Step_i, from Step_x up to Step_(x+y), each strictly and totally ordered, finite sub-set can be partitioned into two equally partitioned, strictly and totally ordered, finite sub-sets. Starting at Step_x, this will generate an exact binomial distribution, with no deviation, of the total number of unique parity sequences at each Step Step_i, from Step_x up to Step_(x+y), with a particular number of even (or odd) steps. This exact binomial distribution continues from Step_x to Step_(x+y).

Proof. Proof is provided by deriving an equation and then evaluating it for two cases, where $i \leq x - 1$ and $i = x$. Proof is then extended by continuous partitioning of sub-sets at each step from Step_x to Step_(x+y) into two equally partitioned, strictly and totally ordered, finite sub-sets. Examples in Table 1, Figures 2 and 3 .

2.1. Derivation of Equation. Any two value-less integers n_1 and n_2 that are sequential elements of any properly defined, strictly and totally ordered, finite sub-set $I_j \in \mathbb{N}_1$, where $x \in \mathbb{N}_0$, may be logically represented, at Step₀, as:

$$(2.1) \quad n_2 = n_1 + 1 * 2^x \quad \text{where: } n_1 < n_2 \text{ and } n_1 \equiv n_2 \pmod{2}^1$$

since all sequential integers are exactly 2^x apart. A proof for any two value-less sequential elements of any sub-set I_j is sufficient to prove the theorem.

Using Equation 1.1 and substituting Equation 2.1 for n_2 yields:

$$\begin{aligned} f^i(n_1) &= \frac{(3^p * n_1 + b_1)}{2^i} \\ f^i(n_2) &= \frac{(3^p * n_2 + b_2)}{2^i} = \frac{(3^p * (n_1 + 1 * 2^x) + b_2)}{2^i} \end{aligned}$$

Since $n_2 > n_1$, therefore $f^i(n_2) > f^i(n_1)$, at least until $f^i(n_2) \not\equiv f^i(n_1) \pmod{2}$, and the following is true: ²

$$\text{If } (f^i(n_2) - f^i(n_1)) \pmod{2} \equiv 0, \text{ then } f^i(n_2) \equiv f^i(n_1) \pmod{2}$$

$$\text{If } (f^i(n_2) - f^i(n_1)) \pmod{2} \equiv 1, \text{ then } f^i(n_2) \not\equiv f^i(n_1) \pmod{2}$$

¹With the exception of sub-set $I_1 = \{n \mid 1 + m * 2^x \text{ where } m \in \mathbb{N}_0 \text{ and } x = 0\}$, before Step₁ (after Step₀), since $I_1 = \mathbb{N}_1$, which is already of alternating parity. Proof in Case 2.

²Although trivial, it is stated that, for any integers a and b , for $a - b$, where $a > b$, odd - odd = even, even - even = even, odd - even = odd and even - odd = odd.

Using “(I/A)” as the Identical/Alternating (mod 2) variable, where Identical Parity = 0 and Alternating Parity = 1:

$$(f^i(n_2) - f^i(n_1)) \pmod{2} \equiv (I/A)$$

Substitute:

$$\left(\frac{(3^p * (n_1 + 1 * 2^x) + b_2)}{2^i} - \frac{(3^p * n_1 + b_1)}{2^i} \right) \pmod{2} \equiv (I/A)$$

Until the first time $f^i(n_2) \not\equiv f^i(n_1) \pmod{2}$, this simplifies to: ³

$$\left(\frac{3^p * n_1 + 3^p * 2^x + b_2}{2^i} - \frac{3^p * n_1 + b_1}{2^i} \right) \pmod{2} \equiv (I/A)$$

$$\left(\frac{\cancel{3^p * n_1} - \cancel{3^p * n_1} + 3^p * 2^x}{2^i} + \frac{\cancel{b_2} - \cancel{b_1}}{2^i} \right) \pmod{2} \equiv (I/A)$$

Yielding:

$$(3^p * 2^{x-i}) \pmod{2} \equiv (I/A)^4$$

Therefore, if:

$$(3^p * 2^{(x-i)}) \pmod{2} \equiv 0 \text{ then } f^i(n_1) \equiv f^i(n_2) \pmod{2}$$

$$(3^p * 2^{(x-i)}) \pmod{2} \equiv 1 \text{ then } f^i(n_1) \not\equiv f^i(n_2) \pmod{2}$$

2.2. Case Evaluations.

2.2.1. *Case 1* ($i \leq x - 1$) *Evaluation.* Not applicable for $x = 0$ since $i \not\leq 0$.
Where: $i \leq x - 1$

$$\begin{aligned} x - i &\geq 1 \\ 2^{(x-i)} \pmod{2} &\equiv 0 \\ 3^p \pmod{2} &\equiv 1 \end{aligned}$$

Evaluating:

$$(3^p * 2^{x-i}) \equiv (I/A)$$

$$\text{odd} * \text{even} \equiv \text{even}$$

$$\therefore (3^p * 2^{(x-i)}) \pmod{2} \equiv 0$$

\therefore Case 1 results in $f^i(n_1) \equiv f^i(n_2) \pmod{2}$ after all Steps_{*i*} up to and including Step _{$(x-1)$} and resulting in Identical Parity Sequences up to and including Step_{*x*} for all elements of any strictly and totally ordered, finite sub-set I_j .

³Until the first time $f^i(n_2) \not\equiv f^i(n_1) \pmod{2}$, both will have followed exactly the same parity sequence, so $b_1 = b_2$.

⁴Although trivial, it is stated that, for any integers a and b , for $a * b$, odd * odd = odd, even * even = even, odd * even = even and even * odd = even.

2.2.2. *Case 2 (i = x) Evaluation.* Applicable for $x \geq 0$ since $i \geq 0$.
Where: $i = x$

$$\begin{aligned} x - i &= 0 \\ 2^{(x-i)} \pmod{2} &\equiv 1 \\ 3^p \pmod{2} &\equiv 1 \end{aligned}$$

Evaluating:

$$\begin{aligned} 3^p * 2^{(x-i)} &\equiv (I/A) \\ \text{odd} * \text{odd} &\equiv \text{odd} \\ \therefore (3^p * 2^{(x-i)}) \pmod{2} &\equiv 1 \end{aligned}$$

\therefore Case 2 results in $f^i(n_1) \not\equiv f^i(n_2) \pmod{2}$ after Step_x and with an Alternating Parity Sequence at $\text{Step}_{(x+1)}$, after which, $b_1 \neq b_2$ for any two sequential elements of any strictly and totally ordered, finite sub-set I_j .

2.3. **Proof Extension.** Equally partitioning of any I_j into two, strictly and totally ordered, finite sub-sets, I_a and I_b where:

$$\begin{aligned} I_a \cup I_b &= I_j \\ |I_a| = |I_b| &= 2^{(y-1)} = \frac{|I_j|}{2} \\ I_a &= \{n_1, n_3, n_5, \dots, n_{(2^y-1)}\} = \{a_1, a_2, a_3, \dots, a_{(2^{(y-1)})}\} \\ I_b &= \{n_2, n_4, n_6, \dots, n_{(2^y)}\} = \{b_1, b_2, b_3, \dots, b_{(2^{(y-1)})}\} \\ a_1 &< b_1 < a_2 < b_2 < a_3 < b_3 < \dots < a_{(2^{(y-1)})} < b_{(2^{(y-1)})} \\ I_a &= \{a \mid a = j + m * 2^{(x+1)} \text{ for all } m \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, 2^{(y-1)} - 1\}\} \\ I_b &= \{b \mid b = (j + 2^x) + m * 2^{(x+1)} \text{ for all } m \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, 2^{(y-1)} - 1\}\} \end{aligned}$$

will result in, immediately after Step_x , for all $a_O \in I_a$ and $b_O \in I_b$:

$$\begin{aligned} f^x(a_O) &\not\equiv f^x(b_O) \pmod{2} \\ f^x(a_1) &\equiv f^x(a_2) \equiv \dots \equiv f^x(a_{(2^{(y-1)})}) \pmod{2} \\ f^x(b_1) &\equiv f^x(b_2) \equiv \dots \equiv f^x(b_{(2^{(y-1)})}) \pmod{2} \end{aligned}$$

Prior to every Step_i , from Step_x up to $\text{Step}_{(x+y)}$, each equally partitioned, strictly and totally ordered, finite sub-set can again be partitioned into two equally partitioned, strictly and totally ordered, finite sub-sets. Starting at Step_x , this will generate an exact binomial distribution, with no deviation, of the total number of unique parity sequences at each Step_i , from Step_x up to $\text{Step}_{(x+y)}$, with a particular number of even (or odd) steps. This exact binomial distribution continues from Step_x to $\text{Step}_{(x+y)}$.

Prior to $\text{Step}_{(x+y)}$, every sub-set, $I_{\text{Step}_{(x+y)}} \in I_j$, only has one element where:

$$|I_{\text{Step}_{(x+y)}}| = 2^{(y-y)} = \frac{|I_j|}{2^y} = 1$$

and, therefore, cannot be further equally partitioned, ending the exact binomial distribution after $\text{Step}_{(x+y)}$. It follows directly by this proof, that increasing the original value of y by any amount, would extend the exact binomial distribution to after the new $\text{Step}_{(x+y)}$ and, using L'Hôpital's rule, extending $y \rightarrow \infty$ yields:

$$\lim_{y \rightarrow \infty} |I_{\text{Step}_{(x+y)}}| = 1$$

2.4. Proof Conclusion. It has been proved that recursively applying the Short-cut Collatz function to all elements of any of the previously defined equally partitioned, strictly and totally ordered, sub-sets I_j of \mathbb{N}_1 will result in exactly identical parity sequences, for all $n_O \in I_j$, up to and including Step_x . Immediately after Step_x , the parity of $f^x(n_O)$, for each sequential element of sub-set I_j , will alternate.

It is also proved, by extension, as $y \rightarrow \infty$, that an exact binomial distribution, with no deviation, of the total number of unique parity sequences at each Step_i , from Step_x up to $\text{Step}_{(x+y)}$, with a particular number of even (or odd) steps, will be generated from Step_x to $\text{Step}_{(x+y)}$. \square

3. INFINITE BINOMIAL EXPANSION COROLLARY

Corollary 3.1. By extension of the Identical and Alternating Parity Equivalence Theorem, recursively and equally partitioning the strictly and totally ordered, infinite set, $\mathbb{N}_1 = I_1 = \{n \mid 1 + m * 2^x \text{ for all } m \in \mathbb{N}_0 \text{ where } x = i = 0\}$, prior to each Step_i of the Short-cut Collatz function, produces, prior to each Step_i , 2^i equally partitioned, strictly and totally ordered, infinite sub-sets where:

$$\begin{aligned} x &= i \\ I_j &\in \{I_1, I_2, I_3, \dots, I_{(2^x)}\} \\ I_j &= \{n \mid j + m * 2^x \text{ for all } m \in \mathbb{N}_0\} \\ |I_j| &= |\mathbb{N}_1| \end{aligned}$$

When the sub-sets, I_j , for Step_i are sorted and totaled according to the number of even (or odd) steps, after Step_i , in each sub-set's unique parity sequence, it produces a perfect row (r) for Pascal's Triangle, where $r = i$ and, as $i \rightarrow \infty$, generates an infinite and exact binomial distribution, with no deviation, from Step_0 to Step_i . If it were possible to carry this forward to Step_∞ , every equally partitioned, strictly and totally ordered, infinite sub-set I_j of the set, \mathbb{N}_1 , would have a unique sequence, including the theoretical sub-sets where:

$$\begin{aligned} I_j &\in \{I_1, I_2, I_3, \dots, I_{\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} 2^x}\} \\ I_j &= \{n \mid j + m * \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} 2^x \text{ for all } m \in \mathbb{N}_0\} \end{aligned}$$

Proof. After Step_x , equally partitioning the sub-set I_j will result in two new sub-sets, which, using the original values of j and x , will be:

$$\begin{aligned} I_j &= \{n \mid j + m * 2^{(x+1)} \text{ for all } m \in \mathbb{N}_0\} \\ I_{(j+2^x)} &= \{n \mid (j + 2^x) + m * 2^{(x+1)} \text{ for all } m \in \mathbb{N}_0\} \end{aligned}$$

To maintain an identical parity sequences at each Step_i , starting at Step_0 , where $x = i = 0$, $q = 0 = \text{even Steps}$ and $PS_i = \text{Parity Sequence at Step}_i$, the sub-set:

$$\mathbb{N}_1 = I_1 = \{1, 2, 3, \dots\} = \{n \mid 1 + m * 2^0 \text{ for all } m \in \mathbb{N}_0\} \rightarrow PS_0 = \emptyset \text{ and } q = 0$$

which produces the first row (1) of Pascal's Triangle of the total number of sub-sets I_j with a particular value of q (or p), must be equally partitioned to:

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 &= \{1, 3, 5, \dots\} = \{n \mid 1 + m * 2^1 \text{ for all } m \in \mathbb{N}_0\} \rightarrow PS_1 = 1 \text{ and } q = 0 \\ I_2 &= \{2, 4, 6, \dots\} = \{n \mid 2 + m * 2^1 \text{ for all } m \in \mathbb{N}_0\} \rightarrow PS_1 = 0 \text{ and } q = 1 \end{aligned}$$

which produces the second row (1, 1) of Pascal's Triangle of the total number of sub-sets I_j with a particular value of q (or p), which must be equally partitioned again to:

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 &= \{1, 5, 9 \dots\} = \{n \mid 1 + m * 2^2 \text{ for all } m \in \mathbb{N}_0\} \rightarrow PS_2 = 10 \text{ and } q = 1 \\ I_3 &= \{3, 7, 11 \dots\} = \{n \mid 3 + m * 2^2 \text{ for all } m \in \mathbb{N}_0\} \rightarrow PS_2 = 11 \text{ and } q = 0 \\ I_2 &= \{2, 6, 10 \dots\} = \{n \mid 2 + m * 2^2 \text{ for all } m \in \mathbb{N}_0\} \rightarrow PS_2 = 01 \text{ and } q = 1 \\ I_4 &= \{4, 8, 12 \dots\} = \{n \mid 4 + m * 2^2 \text{ for all } m \in \mathbb{N}_0\} \rightarrow PS_2 = 00 \text{ and } q = 2 \end{aligned}$$

which produces the third row (1, 2, 1) of Pascal's Triangle of the total number of sub-sets I_j with a particular value of q (or p), which must be equally partitioned again to:

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 &= \{1, 9, 17 \dots\} = \{n \mid 1 + m * 2^3 \text{ for all } m \in \mathbb{N}_0\} \rightarrow PS_3 = 101 \text{ and } q = 1 \\ I_5 &= \{5, 13, 21 \dots\} = \{n \mid 5 + m * 2^3 \text{ for all } m \in \mathbb{N}_0\} \rightarrow PS_3 = 100 \text{ and } q = 2 \\ I_3 &= \{3, 11, 19 \dots\} = \{n \mid 3 + m * 2^3 \text{ for all } m \in \mathbb{N}_0\} \rightarrow PS_3 = 110 \text{ and } q = 1 \\ I_7 &= \{7, 15, 23 \dots\} = \{n \mid 7 + m * 2^3 \text{ for all } m \in \mathbb{N}_0\} \rightarrow PS_3 = 111 \text{ and } q = 0 \\ I_2 &= \{2, 10, 18 \dots\} = \{n \mid 2 + m * 2^3 \text{ for all } m \in \mathbb{N}_0\} \rightarrow PS_3 = 010 \text{ and } q = 2 \\ I_6 &= \{6, 14, 22 \dots\} = \{n \mid 6 + m * 2^3 \text{ for all } m \in \mathbb{N}_0\} \rightarrow PS_3 = 011 \text{ and } q = 1 \\ I_4 &= \{4, 12, 20 \dots\} = \{n \mid 4 + m * 2^3 \text{ for all } m \in \mathbb{N}_0\} \rightarrow PS_3 = 001 \text{ and } q = 2 \\ I_8 &= \{8, 16, 24 \dots\} = \{n \mid 8 + m * 2^3 \text{ for all } m \in \mathbb{N}_0\} \rightarrow PS_3 = 000 \text{ and } q = 3 \end{aligned}$$

which produces the fourth row (1, 3, 3, 1) of Pascal's Triangle of the total number of sub-sets I_j with a particular value of q (or p), which must be equally partitioned again ... ad infinitum.

Since any sub-set I_j can be infinitely evenly partitioned, this proof extends to infinity, producing an infinite and exact binomial distribution, with no deviation, of the total number of equally partitioned sub-sets I_j , where $x = i$, each with its own unique parity sequence, at each Step $_i$, with a particular value of q (or p). \square

4. MIRROR SUB-SET AND MIRROR PARITY SEQUENCE COROLLARY

Corollary 4.1. There exist, for any Step $_i$, exactly $2^{(i-1)}$ pairs of bilaterally symmetrical parity sequences when plotted as on Figure 4. The line of symmetry is formed by $y = x$, $q = p$ or $\frac{\text{Even Steps}}{\text{Odd Steps}} = 1$. Each pair of bilaterally symmetrical parity sequences is produced, up to Step $_i$, by two "mirror" equally partitioned, strictly and totally ordered, infinite sub-sets, I_{TI} and I_{MI} where:⁵

$$\begin{aligned} I_{TI} &= \{n \mid TI + m * 2^i \text{ for all } m \in \mathbb{N}_0\} \\ I_{MI} &= \{n \mid MI + m * 2^i \text{ for all } m \in \mathbb{N}_0\} \end{aligned}$$

Definition 4.2. Energy Value = $EV = \frac{q}{p} = \frac{\text{Even Steps}}{\text{Odd Steps}}$

The ratio of $\frac{\text{Even Steps}}{\text{Odd Steps}}$ for MI , at Step $_i$, will be the inverse of the ratio of $\frac{\text{Even Steps}}{\text{Odd Steps}}$ for TI , from Step $_1$, up to and including Step $_i$. This may or may not continue past Step $_i$.

$$\therefore EV_{MI} = \frac{1}{EV_{TI}} \text{ "at least" for all Steps}_{0 \rightarrow i}$$

⁵ TI (Test Integer) and MI (Mirror Integer) are the least elements of their respective sub-sets.

Proof. The previous proofs show that, at Step_{*i*}, all elements of each infinite sub-set I_j , where $x = i$, will produce a unique parity sequence up to and including Step_{*i*} and that all possible parity sequences will be produced. Therefore for any positive integer TI taken through Step_{*i*}, logically there will be:

- ∞ integers that follow an identical parity sequence up to Step_{*i*}
- ∞ integers that follow a bilaterally symmetrical parity sequence up to Step_{*i*}
 - “Mirror” integers will always have opposite initial parity.

Although proof of the Mirror Sub-set and Mirror Parity Sequence Corollary follows logically from the proofs of the Identical and Alternating Parity Equivalence Theorem and Infinite Binomial Expansion Corollary, three examples are provided using the least elements, TI , MI , and BA , of several equally partitioned, strictly and totally ordered, infinite sub-sets, I_{TI} , I_{MI} and I_{BA} .

Lemma 4.3 (Finding the Mirror Sub-set). *Determining the MI for a particular TI is not difficult. See sample Simple R Code and Output in Appendix B. First determine the parity sequence for the TI up to whatever Step_{*i*} you desire to show bilateral symmetry for. Then invert the parity sequence such that, where PS = parity sequence:*

$$PS_{TI} = 1101111101 \dots \Leftrightarrow PS_{MI} = 0010000010 \dots$$

Next, starting with:

$$\mathbb{N}_1 = I_1 = \{1, 2, 3, \dots\} = \{n \mid 1 + m * 2^x \text{ for all } m \in \mathbb{N}_0 \text{ where } x = i = 0\}$$

recursively and equally partition each surviving strictly and totally ordered, infinite sub-set I_j such that:

$$I_j = \{n \mid j + m * 2^{(x+1)} \text{ for all } m \in \mathbb{N}_0\}$$

$$I_{(j+2^x)} = \{n \mid (j + 2^x) + m * 2^{(x+1)} \text{ for all } m \in \mathbb{N}_0\}$$

After each partition, determine which of the two sub-sets meets the requirements for the next parity step in the mirror parity sequence and eliminate the other sub-set. Repeat the process of partitioning and eliminating until $x = i$ for the Step_{*i*} desired. The least element for the last surviving sub-set is the MI.

Example 4.4. A Test Integer, $TI = 27$, the least element of the equally partitioned, strictly and totally ordered, infinite sub-set I_{TI} where:

$$I_{27} = \{n \mid 27 + m * 2^{100} \text{ for all } m \in \mathbb{N}_0\}$$

and which solves to 1 in 70 Short-cut Collatz Steps, is plotted on Figure 4.

The Mirror Integer, MI , the least element of the equally partitioned, strictly and totally ordered, infinite sub-set I_{MI} where:

$$I_{MI} = \{n \mid MI + m * 2^{100} \text{ for all } m \in \mathbb{N}_0\}$$

$$MI = 471, 118, 234, 108, 803, 797, 791, 324, 418, 132$$

and which solves to 1 in 598 Short-cut Collatz Steps, is also plotted on Figure 4. The MI is the least element of \mathbb{N}_1 that mirrors, with perfect bilateral symmetry, the TI parity sequence up to Step₁₀₀. The MI undergoes 2 even steps before it first becomes odd.

$$MI_{1^{st} \text{ Odd}} = 117, 779, 558, 527, 200, 949, 447, 831, 104, 533$$

Example 4.5. A Break Away Integer, BA , the least element of the equally partitioned, strictly and totally ordered, infinite sub-set I_{BA} where:

$$I_{BA} = \{n \mid BA + m * 2^{49} \text{ for all } m \in \mathbb{N}_0\}$$

$$BA = 556,440,017,350,740$$

and which solves to 1 in 111 Short-cut Collatz Steps, is also plotted on Figure 4. The BA is the least element of \mathbb{N}_1 that mirrors, with perfect bilateral symmetry, the TI parity sequence up to Step₄₉. The BA parity sequence is identical to the MI parity sequence up to Step₄₉. The BA undergoes 2 even steps before it first becomes odd.

$$BA_{1^{st} \text{ Odd}} = 139,110,004,337,685$$

Note that the MI is the 836,874,097,325,342nd element of the equally partitioned, strictly and totally ordered, infinite sub-set I_{BA} .

$$MI \in I_{BA}$$

$$MI = BA + 836874097325341 * 2^{49}$$

Example 4.6. If the infinite sub-set $I_{BA} \in \{n \mid BA + m * 2^{49} \text{ for all } m \in \mathbb{N}_0\}$ was limited to a finite sub-set $I_{BA} \in \{j \mid BA + m * 2^{49} \text{ for all } m \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, (2^{49} - 1)\}\}$ and all elements of the sub-set were plotted for all Steps up to Step₉₈, they would follow the MI sequence up to Step₄₉ and then split to form a perfect Pascal's Triangle binomial distribution shown by the Pascal Envelope in Figure 4 up to Step₉₈.⁶

□

5. $EV > EEV$ THEOREM AND $EV > 1$ LEMMA

5.1. $EV > EEV$ Theorem.

Theorem 5.1. For any equally partitioned, strictly and totally ordered, infinite sub-set I_j , where $x = i$, **the first time** that any $n_O \in I_j$ results in $EV > EEV$ at Step _{i} , then $f^i(n_O) \leq n_O$. By extension $f^i(n_O) \leq n_O$ for all $n_O \in I_j$ at Step _{i} , since it was proven, in the previous theorem, that all $n_O \in I_j$, where $x = i$, have identical parity sequences up to Step _{i} .

Definition 5.2. Escape Energy Value = $EEV = (\log_2(3) - 1)$

Proof. Proof is trivial for all $n_O \pmod{2} \equiv 0$. For all $n_O \in I_2$, where:

$$I_2 = \{2, 4, 6 \dots 2 + (2^y - 1) * 2^x\} \text{ where } x = i = 1$$

result in $EV = \frac{q}{p} = \frac{1}{0}$ and $f^i(n_O) < n_O$ after the Step₁ and $\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{x} \ggg EEV$.

Proof for all $n_O \pmod{2} \equiv 1$ provided by evaluating 3 Cases where:

$$(5.1) \quad EV + v = \frac{q}{p} + v = \log_2(3) - 1 = EEV$$

⁶There will be only one element of this finite sub-set I_{BA} which, after Step₄₉, will undergo continuous odd Steps until Step₉₈ and only one element of this finite sub-set I_{BA} which, after Step₄₉, will undergo continuous even Steps until Step₉₈

Case 1: $\frac{q}{p} = \log_2(3) - 1$ where $(v = 0)$

Case 2: $\frac{q}{p} < \log_2(3) - 1$ where $(v > 0)$

Case 3: $\frac{q}{p} > \log_2(3) - 1$ where $(v < 0)$

5.2. Derivation of Equation.

Given, from Equation 5.1:

$$\frac{q}{p} + v = \log_2(3) - 1$$

Rearranging yields:

$$q = p * \log_2(3) - p - v * p$$

Combining Equation 1.1 and 1.3:

$$f^i(n_O) = n_O + w = \frac{3^p * n_O}{2^i} + \frac{b}{2^i}$$

Since $2^i = 2^{(p+q)} = 2^p * 2^q$, substituting yields:

$$n_O + w = \frac{3^p * n_O}{2^p * 2^q} + \frac{b}{2^p * 2^q}$$

Since $q = p * \log_2(3) - p - v * p$, substituting yields:

$$n_O + w = \frac{3^p * n_O}{2^p * 2^{p * \log_2(3) - p - v * p}} + \frac{b}{2^p * 2^{p * \log_2(3) - p - v * p}}$$

Condensing, rearranging and cancelling since $2^{p * \log_2(3)} = 3^p$:

$$\begin{aligned} n_O + w &= \frac{3^p * n_O}{2^{p * \log_2(3)} * 2^{-v * p}} + \frac{b}{2^{p * \log_2(3)} * 2^{-v * p}} \\ n_O + w &= \left(\frac{3^p}{2^{p * \log_2(3)}} * 2^{v * p} * n_O \right) + \left(\frac{b}{3^p} * 2^{v * p} \right) \\ n_O + w &= \left(2^{v * p} * n_O \right) + \left(\frac{b}{3^p} * 2^{v * p} \right) \end{aligned}$$

Subtract n_O from both sides:

$$w = \left(2^{v * p} * n_O \right) - n_O + \left(\frac{b}{3^p} * 2^{v * p} \right)$$

Factor out n_O :

$$w = \left(2^{v * p} - 1 \right) * n_O + \left(\frac{b}{3^p} * 2^{v * p} \right)$$

Simplify by substitution:

$$w = \left(V - 1 \right) * n_O + B * V = R * n_O + B * V$$

Where, if $p \geq 1$:

$$G_0 > 0 \text{ and } G_1 > 1 \text{ (Used for clarity of analysis)}$$

$$B = \frac{b}{3^p} = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{3} \leq B < 1 & \therefore 0 < B < 1 & \text{if } n_O \pmod{2} \equiv 1 \\ 0 \leq B < 1 & \therefore 0 \leq B < 1 & \text{if } n_O \pmod{2} \equiv 0 \end{cases}$$

$$V = 2^{v*2^p} = \begin{cases} 2^{0*2^p} = 1 & \therefore V = 1 & \text{if } v = 0 \\ 2^{G_0*2^p} > 1 & \therefore V > 1 \text{ and } V = G_1 & \text{if } v > 0 \\ 0 < \frac{1}{2^{|v|*2^p}} < 1 & \therefore 0 < V < 1 & \text{if } v < 0 \end{cases}$$

$$R = V - 1 = \begin{cases} 1 - 1 = 0 & \therefore R = 0 & \text{if } v = 0 \\ G_1 - 1 & \therefore R > 0 \text{ and } R = G_0 & \text{if } v > 0 \\ 0 - 1 < R < 1 - 1 & \therefore -1 < R < 0 & \text{if } v < 0 \end{cases}$$

5.3. Case Evaluations.

5.3.1. *Case 1* ($v = 0$) *Evaluation.* For $n_O \pmod{2} \equiv 1$ where:

$$\begin{aligned} 0 < B < 1 \\ V &= 1 \\ R &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

Given $w = R * n_O + B * V$:

$$\begin{aligned} w &= 0 * n_{\text{Original}} + B * 1 \\ w &= B \end{aligned}$$

This is not possible since:

$$\begin{aligned} B &\neq \text{Integer} \\ w &= \text{Integer} \\ w &\neq B \text{ and } v \neq 0 \text{ and } \frac{q}{p} \neq \log_2(3) - 1 \end{aligned}$$

\therefore Case 1 where $v = 0$ is not possible.

5.3.2. *Case 2* ($v > 0$) *Evaluation.* For $n_O \pmod{2} \equiv 1$ where:

$$\begin{aligned} 0 < B < 1 \\ V &> 1 \text{ and } V = G_1 \\ R &> 0 \text{ and } R = G_0 \end{aligned}$$

Given $w = R * n_O + B * V$:

$$\begin{aligned} w &= G_0 * n_O + B * G_1 \\ w &> 0 \\ w &\geq 1 \text{ (since } w = \text{Integer)} \end{aligned}$$

\therefore For Case 2 where $v > 0$ since:

$$\begin{aligned} f^i(n_O) &= n_O + w \\ f^i(n_O) &> n_O \end{aligned}$$

5.3.3. *Case 3* ($v < 0$) *Evaluation.* For $n_O \pmod{2} \equiv 1$ where:

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &< B < 1 \\ 0 &< V < 1 \\ -1 &< R < 0 \end{aligned}$$

Given $w = R * n_O + B * V$:

$$-n_O < R * n_O < 0$$

$$0 < B * V < 1$$

$$-n_O < w < 1$$

$$-n_O + 1 \leq w \leq 0 \text{ (since } w = \text{Integer)}$$

Since:

$$f^i(n_O) = n_O + w$$

Three Sub-Cases:

(1) If $w = -n_O + 1$, then:

$$n_O + (-n_O + 1) = 1$$

starting the known terminal loop sequence, $\{1, 2, 1, 2, \dots \infty\}$.

(2) If $w = 0$ then:

$$n_O + 0 = n_O$$

starting either the known terminal loop sequence or another, yet to be discovered, terminal loop sequence, which is proved in the next theorem not to exist.

(3) If $-n_O + 1 < w < 0$ then, since $w < 0$:

$$n_O + w < n_O$$

\therefore For Case 3 where $v < 0$ and $EV > EEV$:

$$f^i(n_O) \leq n_O$$

$$f^i(n_O) < n_O \text{ or } f^i(n_O) = n_O \text{ starting a Terminal Loop}$$

5.4. **Proof Conclusion.** Refer to Figures 5 and 6.

Case 1 shows it impossible for $EV = EEV$.

Case 2 shows that if $EV < EEV$ then $f^i(n_O) > n_O$.

Logically, if $EV < EEV$ for all Steps $_{1 \rightarrow \infty}$ then $f^i(n_O) > n_O$ for all Steps $_{1 \rightarrow \infty}$

Case 3 shows that if $EV > EEV$ then either:

$$f^i(n_O) < n_O \text{ or } f^i(n_O) = n_O \text{ starting a Terminal Loop}$$

Therefore the $EV > EEV$ Theorem is proved true. \square

5.5. **$EV > 1$ Lemma.** Although it has also been proven in the $EV > EEV$ Theorem that, for n_O , **the first time:**

$$EV > EEV \text{ then } f^i(n_O) < n_O$$

this is not true at all Steps $_{i_{plus}}$, past the first Step $_i$ where $EV > EEV$, for all n_O .

There are 593 outliers for $n_O \leq 4614$, that, although the n_O solved to $f^i(n_O) < n_O$ at Step $_i$, there are instances, in some cases multiple instances, where $f^{i_{plus}}(n_O) > n_O$ at a later Step $_{i_{plus}}$, although $EV > EEV$ at Step $_{i_{plus}}$. These outliers are discussed in Appendix C.

For a strong proof of the No Infinite Divergence Theorem, presented later in this paper, the following Lemma is provided with an extremely limited condition where $f^i(n_O) < n_O$ for all Steps $_{1 \rightarrow i}$ until $f^i(n_O) = 1$, where there is no possibility of outliers.

Lemma 5.3. *For all $n_O \in \mathbb{N}_1 > 2$, if the $EV > 1$ for all Steps $_{1 \rightarrow i}$, where $i \leq n_O$ then:*

$$f^i(n_O) < n_O \text{ for all Steps}_{1 \rightarrow i} \text{ until } f^i(n_O) = 1$$

Proof. Where:

$$v \in \mathbb{N}_1 \quad (v \geq 1)$$

$$q = p + v$$

$$EV = \frac{q}{p} = \frac{p+v}{p} > 1$$

$$i = q + p = 2 * p + v$$

Using Equation 1.1:

$$f^i(n_O) = \frac{3^p * n_O + b}{2^i} = \frac{3^p}{2^{(2*p+v)}} * n_O + \frac{b}{2^{(2*p+v)}}$$

To maintain $EV > 1$, the range of parity sequences must be between (0000 $\overline{00}$...) and (0010 $\overline{10}$...), until $f^i(n_O) = 1$, so all n_O must go through at least 2 even steps first. The lowest n_O that will undergo at least 2 even steps first is $n_O = 4$.

After 2 even steps, $v = 2$ and $p = 0$ therefore $\frac{3^p}{2^{(2*p+v)}} = .25$ and $\frac{b}{2^{(2*p+v)}} = 0$. Then as p or v increase, $\frac{3^p}{2^{(2*p+v)}}$ decreases $\rightarrow 0$ and $\frac{b}{2^{(2*p+v)}}$ increases $\rightarrow 2$.

$$0 < \frac{3^p}{2^{(2*p+v)}} \leq 0.25 \text{ and } 0 \leq \frac{b}{2^{(2*p+v)}} < 2$$

$$0 < f^i(n_O) < 0.25 * n_O + 2$$

$$\therefore f^i(n_O) < n_O \text{ for all Steps}_{1 \rightarrow i} \text{ until } f^i(n_O) = 1$$

For any n_O there are only $[n_O - 1]$ integers that are $< n_O$. Therefore, logically, at or before Step $_{n_O}$, $f^i(n_O) = 1$, starting the known terminal loop sequence. Where

$f^i(n_O) < n_O$ for all Steps $_{1 \rightarrow i}$ and $EV > 1$ for all Steps $_{1 \rightarrow i}$, $f^i(n_O)$ will first equal 1 significantly before Step $_{n_O}$ (\lesssim Step $_{4.819 * \log_2(n_O)}$).^{7,8}

Therefore, for all $n_O \in \mathbb{N}_1 > 2$, if the $EV > 1$ for all Steps $_{1 \rightarrow i}$, where $i \leq n_O$, then $f^i(n_O) < n_O$ for all Steps $_{1 \rightarrow i}$ until eventually it must result in $f^i(n_O) = 1$, after which the sequence enters the known terminal loop sequence. \square

6. NO NON-TRIVIAL TERMINAL LOOP SEQUENCES THEOREM

Theorem 6.1. *There are no terminal periodic sequences possible other than the known terminal periodic sequence of (1, 2) of period 2.*

Proof of this theorem eliminates the very slight possibility that $f^i(n_O) = n_O$ for $n_O \in \mathbb{N}_1 > 1$ discovered in the proof of the $EV > EEV$ Theorem.

Proof. Proof is provided by evaluation of a Special Case of Case 3 of the $EV > EEV$ Theorem followed by logical analysis.

6.1. Case Evaluation, Analysis and Final Proof.

6.1.1. Special Case Evaluation of Case 3 of the $EV > EEV$ Theorem.

Given from Case 3, where $v < 0$ and $w = 0$:

$$\begin{aligned} -n_O &< R * n_O < 0 \\ 0 &< B * V < 1 \\ V &= \frac{1}{2^{|v|*p}} \\ w &= R * n_O + B * V \end{aligned}$$

$w = 0$ only if:

$$|R * n_O| = B * V$$

Then the following must be true:

$$\begin{aligned} -1 &< R * n_O < 0 \\ -\frac{1}{n_O} &< (V - 1) * n_O < 0 \\ -\frac{1}{n_O} &< \left(\frac{1}{2^{|v|*p}} - 1\right) < 0 \\ \text{(Solving for } n_O \text{ so right side of inequality is unnecessary)} \\ \text{(Multiply by -1)} \quad \frac{1}{n_O} &> \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^{|v|*p}}\right) \quad \text{(Reverses inequality)} \\ \text{(Invert)} \quad n_O &< \frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{2^{|v|*p}}} \quad \text{(Reverses inequality)} \end{aligned}$$

⁷Although not critical to the proof, the line intercept of the two line equations $q = p + 2$ and $q = \log_2(n_O) + p * EEV$ and two (simplified) trigonometric solutions where $AT = \arctan(EEV)$:

$$2 + 2 * \left(\sin(AT) * \left[\sin\left(\frac{\pi}{2} - AT\right) + \tan\left(\frac{\pi}{4} + AT\right) * \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2} - AT\right) \right] \right) \approx 4.81884168$$

$$2 + 2 * \left(\left[(\sin(AT))^2 + \sin(AT) * \cos(AT) \right] * \left[1 + EEV * \tan(2 * AT) \right] \right) \approx 4.81884168$$

all show that the actual maximum number of steps before $f^i(n_O) = 1$ for any $n_O \in \mathbb{N}_1 > 2$, if the $EV > 1$ for all Steps $_{1 \rightarrow i}$ is less than approximately $4.819 * \log_2(n_O)$.

⁸Step $_{n_O}$ is only a hard maximum limit for the number of steps before $f^i(n_O) = 1$ where $f^i(n_O) < n_O$ for all Steps $_{1 \rightarrow i}$ and $EV > EEV$ for all Steps $_{1 \rightarrow i}$.

Therefore:

$$(6.1) \quad n_O \leq \left\lfloor \frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{2^{|v|*p}}} \right\rfloor \quad (\text{Floor to account for integer values})$$

\therefore Only if $n_O \leq \left\lfloor \frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{2^{|v|*p}}} \right\rfloor$ does there exist a possibility that any terminal loop sequence restarts at Step_{*i*}.

6.1.2. *Analysis and final proof.* For any possible terminal loop sequence, the following should be considered given, intuitive, logical or already proven:

- It must have identical repeating sequence steps with sequence length *i*.
- It must have identical repeating values such that:

$$\begin{aligned} n_O &= f^i(n_O) \\ f^1(n_O) &= f^{(i+1)}(n_O) \\ f^2(n_O) &= f^{(i+2)}(n_O) \\ &\vdots \\ &\vdots \\ f^i(n_O) &= f^{(2*i)}(n_O) \end{aligned}$$

- Any value in the loop must be able to serve as n_O
 - Starting at any n_O in the loop, with $q = p = 0$ initially, must result in
 - * $\frac{q}{p} > (\log_2(3) - 1)$ after *i* Steps
- If loop is started with the lowest value n_O in the loop
 - $n_O \pmod{2} \equiv 1$
 - $f^{(i-1)}(n_O) \pmod{2} \equiv 0$
- With each complete repetition (*r*) of any loop with sequence length *i*
 - The absolute value of *v* ($|v|$), will remain the same since the ratio of even to odd Steps ($\frac{q}{p}$) will remain the same.
 - The value of *p* will increase by a multiple of *r* since all the Steps have increased by a multiple of *r*.
 - Multiple repetitions of a loop are, by definition, a loop also.
 - * For example the value sequences below are functionally equivalent but will provide different mathematical answers, prior to the Floor Function, when used in the Equation 6.1
 - (1, 2) of period 2
 - (1, 2, 1, 2) of period 4
 - (1, 2, 1, 2, 1, 2) of period 6
 - (1, 2, 1, 2, 1, 2, 1, 2) of period 8
- All values of n_O in the loop with sequence length *i*
 - Must satisfy the requirements of Equation 6.1:

$$n_O \leq \left\lfloor \frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{2^{|v|*p}}} \right\rfloor \text{ at Step}_i$$

With ∞ repetitions of any possible loop, $|v|$ will remain constant while *p* will increase towards ∞ and eventually $\left\lfloor \frac{1}{1 - \frac{1}{2^{|v|*p}}} \right\rfloor = 1$. Therefore there is only one possible Shortcut Collatz Function terminal loop sequence $\{1, 2, 1, 2, \dots \infty\}$. \square

7. $EL \geq \log_2(n_O) + p * EEV$ THEOREM

Theorem 7.1. For every $n_O \in \mathbb{N}_1$, **the first time** $EL \geq \log_2(n_O) + p * EEV$, then $f^i(n_O) = 1$.

Definition 7.2. Energy Level = $EL = q =$ even steps at Step _{i}

Proof. Proof for all $n_O \in \mathbb{N}_1$ provided by evaluating 3 Cases where:

$$(7.1) \quad EL + v = \log_2(n_O) + p * EEV$$

Case 1: $EL > \log_2(n_O) + p * EEV$ where $(v < 0)$

Case 2: $EL = \log_2(n_O) + p * EEV$ where $(v = 0)$

Case 3: $EL < \log_2(n_O) + p * EEV$ where $(v > 0)$

7.1. Derivation of Equation for Case Evaluation.

Given, from Equation 7.1:

$$EL + v = q + v = \log_2(n_O) + p * (\log_2(3) - 1) = \log_2(n_O) + p * EEV$$

Rearranging yields:

$$q = \log_2(n_O) + p * (\log_2(3) - 1) - v$$

$$q = \log_2(n_O) + p * (\log_2(3)) - p - v$$

Combining Equation 1.1 and 1.3:

$$f^i(n_O) = n_O + w = \frac{3^p * n_O + b}{2^i}$$

Since $2^i = 2^{(p+q)} = 2^p * 2^q$, substituting yields:

$$n_O + w = \frac{3^p * n_O + b}{2^p * 2^q}$$

Substituting, Condensing and Rearranging:

$$\begin{aligned} n_O + w &= \frac{3^p * n_O + b}{2^p * 2^{\log_2(n_O) + p * (\log_2(3)) - p - v}} \\ n_O + w &= \frac{3^p * n_O + b}{2^{\log_2(n_O)} * 2^{p * (\log_2(3))} * 2^{-v}} \\ n_O + w &= \frac{3^p * n_O + b}{n_O * 3^p * 2^{-v}} \\ n_O + w &= \frac{3^p * n_O}{n_O * 3^p * 2^{-v}} + \frac{b}{n_O * 3^p * 2^{-v}} \\ n_O + w &= \frac{3^p}{3^p} * \frac{n_O}{n_O} * 2^v + \frac{b * 2^v}{n_O * 3^p} \\ n_O + w &= 2^v + \frac{2^v}{n_O} * \frac{b}{3^p} \end{aligned}$$

Simplify by substitution:

$$n_O + w = V + F * B$$

$G_0 > 0$ and $G_1 > 1$ (Used for clarity of analysis)

$$B = \frac{b}{3^p} = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{3} \leq B < 1 & \therefore 0 < B < 1 & \text{if } n_O \pmod{2} \equiv 1 \\ 0 \leq B < 1 & \therefore 0 \leq B < 1 & \text{if } n_O \pmod{2} \equiv 0 \end{cases}$$

$$V = 2^v = \begin{cases} 2^0 = 1 & \therefore V = 1 & \text{if } v = 0 \\ 1 < 2^{G_0} & \therefore 1 < V \text{ and } V = G_1 & \text{if } v > 0 \\ 0 < \frac{1}{2^{|v|}} < 1 & \therefore 0 < V < 1 & \text{if } v < 0 \end{cases}$$

$$F = \frac{2^v}{n_O} = \begin{cases} \frac{2^0}{n_O} = \frac{1}{n_O} & \therefore 0 < F \leq 1 & \text{if } v = 0 \\ \frac{2^{G_0}}{n_O} = \frac{G_1}{n_O} & \therefore 0 < F \text{ and } F = G_0 & \text{if } v > 0 \\ \frac{1}{n_O * 2^{|v|}} & \therefore 0 < F < 1 & \text{if } v < 0 \end{cases}$$

7.2. Case Evaluations.

7.2.1. Case 1 ($v < 0$) Proof Evaluation.

For all $n_O \in \mathbb{N}_1$ where:

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &\leq B < 1 \\ 0 &< V < 1 \\ 0 &< F < 1 \end{aligned}$$

Given $n_O + w = V + F * B$:

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &\leq F * B < 1 \\ 0 &< V + F * B < 2 \\ 0 &< n_O + w < 2 \end{aligned}$$

Since $n_O \in \mathbb{N}_1$ and w is an integer:

$$\text{For Case 1 where } v < 0, f^i(n_O) = n_O + w = 1$$

7.2.2. Case 2 ($v = 0$) Proof Evaluation.

For all $n_O \in \mathbb{N}_1$ where:

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &\leq B < 1 \\ V &= 1 \\ 0 &< F \leq 1 \end{aligned}$$

Given $n_O + w = V + F * B$:

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &\leq F * B < 1 \\ 1 &\leq V + F * B < 2 \\ 1 &\leq n_O + w < 2 \end{aligned}$$

Since $n_O \in \mathbb{N}_1$ and w is an integer:

$$\text{For Case 2 where } v = 0, f^i(n_O) = n_O + w = 1$$

7.2.3. Case 3 ($v > 0$) Proof Evaluation.

For all $n_O \in \mathbb{N}_1$ where:

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &\leq B < 1 \\ 1 &< V \\ 0 &< F \end{aligned}$$

Given $n_O + w = V + F * B$:

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &\leq F * B \\ 1 &< V + F * B \\ 1 &< n_O + w \end{aligned}$$

Since $n_O \in \mathbb{N}_1$ and w is an integer:

$$\text{For Case 3 where } v > 0, f^i(n_O) = n_O + w \geq 2$$

7.3. Proof Conclusion.

Refer to Figures 5 and 6.

Case 3 proves that **until** $EL \geq \log_2(n_O) + p * EEV$ the $f^i(n_O) \geq 2$. Cases 1 and 2 prove that **the first time** $EL \geq \log_2(n_O) + p * EEV$ then the $f^i(n_O) = 1$.

Therefore the $EL \geq \log_2(n_{Original}) + p * EEV$ Theorem is proved true. \square

8. NO INFINITE DIVERGENCE THEOREM

Theorem 8.1. *Every $n_O \in \mathbb{N}_1$, when the Short-cut Collatz function is applied recursively, will eventually result in $f^i(n_O) < n_O$ at some Step _{i} .*

Definition 8.2 (Infinitely Divergent Integer). A Infinitely Divergent Integer is a *theoretical*, but not provably possible or impossible, integer, n_L , for which $f^i(n_L) > n_L$, for all Steps _{i} from $i = 1 \rightarrow \infty$.

Definition 8.3 (Infinitely Convergent Integer). A Infinitely Convergent Integer is a *theoretical*, but provably impossible, integer, n_M , for which $f^i(n_M) < n_M$, for all Steps _{i} from $i = 1 \rightarrow \infty$.

The n_L and n_M would be the least elements of their *theoretical* respective “mirror” equally partitioned, strictly and totally ordered, infinite sub-sets which produce bilaterally symmetrical parity sequences for all Steps _{i} from $i = 1 \rightarrow \infty$.

Proof. Referring to Figure 1, if there exists a lowest divergent integer, n_L , then as proven in the $EV > EEV$ Theorem, it must be true that $EV_{n_L} < EEV$ for all Steps _{$1 \rightarrow \infty$} and $f^i(n_L) > n_L$ for all Steps _{$1 \rightarrow \infty$} . It maybe impossible to directly prove that such an integer, n_L , does or does not exist, since there is an infinite number of integers that are greater than n_L .

However, as has been proven, the Short-cut function of the Collatz Conjecture is a pure infinite binomial expansion and, if n_L does exist, there **must exist** one “mirror” element, $n_M \in \mathbb{N}_1$, whose unique parity sequence is bilaterally symmetrical to that of n_L , and whose EV is the inverse of the EV for the theoretical n_L at all Steps _{i} from $i = 1 \rightarrow \infty$.

Therefore:

$$\begin{aligned} EV_{n_M} &= \frac{1}{EV_{n_L}} \text{ for all Steps}_{1 \rightarrow \infty} \\ EV_{n_M} &> \frac{1}{EEV} \text{ for all Steps}_{1 \rightarrow \infty} \end{aligned}$$

For n_M $\frac{q}{p} > \frac{1}{EEV}$ for all Steps $_{1 \rightarrow \infty}$

For n_M $q > \frac{p}{EEV}$ for all Steps $_{1 \rightarrow \infty}$

For n_M $EL > \frac{p}{EEV}$ for all Steps $_{1 \rightarrow \infty}$

It will be proven that, $n_M \in \mathbb{N}_1$, whose $EV_{n_M} > \frac{1}{EEV}$ for all Steps $_{1 \rightarrow \infty}$ cannot exist and that therefore n_L cannot exist.

As was proved in Lemma 5.3, since for n_M :

$$EV_{n_M} > \frac{1}{EEV} > 1 \text{ for all Steps}_{1 \rightarrow i} \text{ until } f^i(n_M) = 1$$

then

$$f^i(n_M) < n_M \text{ for all Steps}_{1 \rightarrow i} \text{ until } f^i(n_M) = 1$$

It has also been proved in the $EL \geq \log_2(n_O) + p * EEV$ Theorem that, for n_M , the first time:

$$EL \geq \log_2(n_M) + p * EEV \text{ then } f^i(n_M) = 1$$

If the $f^i(n_M) = 1$ limit line for a theoretical n_M were to be plotted on a plot where the y-axis is EL (or even steps) and the x-axis is p (or odd steps) and a theoretical vector for n_M , where the *slope* = $EV_{n_M \text{ at infinity}}$ (*slope* $> \frac{1}{EEV}$) from (0,0), there will always be a point of intersection no matter how great the value of n_M . Where $f^i(n_M) < n_M$ for all Steps $_{1 \rightarrow i}$ and $EV_{n_M} > \frac{1}{EEV}$ for all Steps $_{1 \rightarrow i}$, $f^i(n_M)$ will first equal 1 at $\lesssim \text{Step}_{2.41 * \log_2(n_O)}$.⁹

At this point of intersection, the average *slope* of the sequence for the theoretical n_M would change from *slope* $> \frac{1}{EEV}$ to *slope* = 1, **forever**, since it has entered the Terminal Loop Sequence. Eventually the EV_{n_M} will decrease to $EV_{n_M} < \frac{1}{EEV}$.

This proves that this theoretical n_M is not the “mirror” of the theoretical lowest divergent integer value n_L , since the average *slope* of the sequence for the theoretical “mirror” n_L would also **have to** change from *slope* $< EEV$ to an average *slope* = 1, **again forever**, because it is theoretically a “mirror” sequence of n_M . Since the approach to the Terminal Loop Sequence of the Short-cut Collatz function for all $n_O > 2$ must sequentially pass through the integers 4, 2, 1 with a sequence of 001 and a *slope* > 1 , the only two integers that can create a *slope* = 1 **forever** are 1 and 2 which produce the Terminal Loop Sequence. This would require $f^i(n_L) = 1$ or $f^i(n_L) = 2$ while $EV < EEV$. This is not possible except for $n_L = 1$, whose “mirror” integer is $n_M = 2$ for all Steps $_{1 \rightarrow \infty}$.

Although the new average *slope* = 1 for the n_L cannot continue forever, the EV could increase with an average *slope* = 1 until $EV > EEV$, where $f^i(n_L) < n_L$ and beyond, proving this is not the true lowest divergent integer value n_L .

To summarize and clarify:

- For a given n_L it is always possible to find a mirror n_M up to Step $_i$

⁹Although not critical to the proof, the line intercept of the two line equations $q = \frac{p}{EEV}$ and $q = \log_2(n_O) + p * EEV$ and two (simplified) trigonometric solutions where $AT = \arctan(EEV)$:

$$1 + \sin(AT) * \left[\sin\left(\frac{\pi}{2} - AT\right) + \tan\left(\frac{\pi}{4} + AT\right) * \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2} - AT\right) \right] \approx 2.40942084$$

$$1 + \left[(\sin(AT))^2 + \sin(AT) * \cos(AT) \right] * \left[1 + EEV * \tan(2 * AT) \right] \approx 2.40942084$$

all show that the actual maximum number of steps before $f^i(n_O) = 1$ for any $n_O \in \mathbb{N}_1 > 2$, if the $EV > 1$ for all Steps $_{1 \rightarrow i}$ is less than approximately $2.41 * \log_2(n_O)$.

- Where $EV_{n_M} > \frac{1}{EEV}$ for all Steps_{1→i}, $f^i(n_M) = 1$ at a Step_i < Step_∞
- Increasing the value of the theoretical n_M (or n_L) does nothing but raise the limit line where $f^i(n_M) = 1$ but eventually any theoretical n_M would eventually result in $f^i(n_M) = 1$.
- After $f^i(n_M) = 1$, EV_{n_M} will decrease to $EV_{n_M} < \frac{1}{EEV}$ for all n_M .
- Since there are no values of n_M where $EV_{n_M} > \frac{1}{EEV}$ for all Steps_{1→∞} then there are no values of n_L where $EV_{n_L} < EEV$ for all Steps_{1→∞}

Therefore, it is proved that this theoretical n_M cannot exist and therefore the theoretical lowest divergent integer value n_L cannot exist. Therefore, all $n_O > 1$ are proved to eventually result in $f^i(n_O) < n_O$. \square

9. FINAL PROOF OF COLLATZ CONJECTURE AND THEOREM

Proof. It has been proved that:

- (1) The Short-cut Collatz function is an Infinite Binomial Expansion.
- (2) There exist infinite pairs of “mirror” sub-sets, I_{TI} and I_{MI} , which produce unique infinite bilaterally symmetrical parity sequences.
- (3) There is no unknown terminal periodic sequence.
- (4) A theoretical lowest infinitely convergent integer value n_M cannot exist.
- (5) A theoretical lowest infinitely divergent integer value n_L cannot exist.
- (6) For every $n_O > 1 \in \mathbb{N}_1$, there exists a Step_i, where $f^i(n_O) < n_O$.
- (7) For every $n_O \in \mathbb{N}_1$, there exists a Step_i, where $f^i(n_O) = 1$.

Therefore, the Collatz Conjecture is proved true for all $n_O \in \mathbb{N}_1$. \square

APPENDIX A. EXAMPLE FIGURES AND TABLES

FIGURE 1. Theoretical Infinitely Divergent Integer n_L and Mirror n_M

FIGURE 2. Plot of $n \in \{1, 8193, 16385, \dots, 67100673\}$

FIGURE 3. ZOOMED Plot of $n \in \{1, 8193, 16385, \dots, 67100673\}$

FIGURE 4. Mirror Integer and Break Away Integer of Test Integer 27

Sequence Plots for 16777216 Integers

from $(1 + 0 * 2^0)$ to $(1 + (2^{24} - 1) * 2^0)$
 at intervals of 2^0 for 1000 steps

FIGURE 5. Plot of $n \in \{1, 2, 3, \dots, 16777216(2^{24})\}$

FIGURE 6. Plot of $n \in \{16777217(2^{24} + 1), 16777218, 16777219, \dots, 33554432(2^{25})\}$

TABLE 1. Alternating Parity at 417th Step when adding 2^{416} to TI

Example of Identical and Alternating Parity for 21,407,990,427 tested by adding 2^{416} to TI from 0 to 9 times and running Collatz for 417 steps Presence of ($< n_O$) indicates $n_i < n_O$ after previous parity sequence			
First 416 Parity Sequences IDENTICAL for all Integers At $< n_O$ $EV \approx 0.586206896551724$ $EL = 153$	110111101111011001011011110111110111110111100111010 11011001101100110111111111011101000010111010011101 1111111100101001111011111011111111010101000001110 1100110001110111111101011111110010011110111101101 110111010011000011111100001100110101101111101110 1001101000111000111101000110001111100001101111001 1100111011111111001100011110101111010010100111111 11010001110101100110011011010101110110010100101100 10011010011000(< n_O)00		
Integer ($n_{Original}$)	417 th Parity	Integer ($n_{Original}$)	417 th Parity
$TI = 21,407,990,427$	2	169,230,328,010,303,641,331, 690,318,856,389,386,196,071, 590,247,882,556,495,704,531, 248,437,872,567,112,920,983, 350,278,406,001,133,879,963	1
338,460,656,020,607,282,663, 380,637,712,778,772,392,143, 180,495,765,112,991,409,062, 496,875,745,134,225,841,966, 700,556,811,980,859,769,499	2	507,690,984,030,910,923,995, 070,956,569,168,158,588,214, 770,743,647,669,487,113,593, 745,313,617,701,338,762,950, 050,835,217,960,585,659,035	1

APPENDIX B. SAMPLE CODE TO FIND MIRROR INTEGER

```
##### Simple R Code to determine MI's for given TI #####
NOTE: No error trapping for extremely large integers. Use bigz
class from gmp package or similar for extremely large integers.
TI = 27 # Integer to find mirror for
MirrorSteps = 15 # Step to find mirror to
##### NO CHANGE BELOW #####
TICurrent = TI # Hold value of TI after each Step
TIparity = TICurrent %% 2 # Hold parity of TI after each Step
TIparityString = "" # Hold TI Parity Sequence
TICurrentStep = 0 # Count TI Steps
if (TIparity == 0){MI = 1} # MI for Step 1 if TI is Even
else {MI = 2} # MI for Step 1 if TI is Odd
MICurrent = MI # Hold value of MI after each Step
MIparity = MICurrent %% 2 # Hold parity of MI after each Step
MIparityString = "" # Hold MI Parity Sequence
MICurrentStep = 0 # Count MI Steps
##### START PROGRAM #####
while (TICurrentStep < MirrorSteps){
  ##### DO 1 STEP OF SHORT-CUT COLLATZ ON T1 #####
  if(TICurrent %% 2 == 0){
    TICurrent <- TICurrent/2
    TIparity = 0
    TIparityString = paste(TIparityString, TIparity,sep="")
  }else{
    TICurrent <- (3 * TICurrent +1)/2
    TIparity = 1
    TIparityString = paste(TIparityString, TIparity,sep="")
  }
  ##### FIND PARITY FOR LAST MI AT THIS STEP #####
  MIparityString = "" # Clear for each MI Check
  while (MICurrentStep <= TICurrentStep){
    if(MICurrent %% 2 == 0){
      MICurrent <- MICurrent/2
      MIparity = 0
      MIparityString = paste(MIparityString,
                             MIparity,sep="")
    }else{
      MICurrent <- (3 * MICurrent +1)/2
      MIparity = 1
      MIparityString = paste(MIparityString,
                             MIparity,sep="")
    }
    MICurrentStep = MICurrentStep + 1
  }
}
```

```

##### CHECK IF PARITY IS OPPOSITE AT THIS STEP #####
  if (Miparity == Tiparity){          # NOT OPPOSITE
    MI = MI + 2^(TICurrentStep)      # PARTION TO CORRECT MI
    Micurrent = MI
    ##### REDO SEQUENCE CALC FOR CORRECT MI #####
    MiparityString = ""
    MICurrentStep = 0
    while (MICurrentStep <= TICurrentStep){
      if(Micurrent %% 2 == 0){
        Micurrent <- Micurrent/2
        Miparity = 0
        MiparityString = paste(MiparityString,
                               Miparity,sep="")
      }else{
        Micurrent <- (3 * Micurrent +1)/2
        Miparity = 1
        MiparityString = paste(MiparityString,
                               Miparity,sep="")
      }
      MICurrentStep = MICurrentStep + 1
    }
    Micurrent = MI
  }else{
    MI = MI
    Micurrent = MI
  }
  TICurrentStep = TICurrentStep + 1
##### PRINT AFTER EACH MI FOR EACH STEP FOUND #####
print(paste("Step", TICurrentStep,
            "TI Seq", TIparityString,
            "TI value after Step",TICurrentStep,
            " = ",Ticurrent,sep=" "))
print(paste("Step", MICurrentStep,
            "MI Seq", MIparityString,
            "MI for Step", TICurrentStep,
            "= ",Micurrent,sep=" "))
MICurrentStep = 0
} # LOOP TO FIND MI FOR NEXT STEP
##### END Simple R Code to determine MI's for given TI #####

##### OUTPUT of Sample R Code #####
Step 1 TI Seq 1    TI value after Step 1 = 41
Step 1 MI Seq 0    MI for Step 1 = 2
Step 2 TI Seq 11   TI value after Step 2 = 62
Step 2 MI Seq 00   MI for Step 2 = 4
Step 3 TI Seq 110  TI value after Step 3 = 31
Step 3 MI Seq 001  MI for Step 3 = 4
Step 4 TI Seq 1101 TI value after Step 4 = 47

```

Step 4 MI Seq 0010 MI for Step 4 = 4
 Step 5 TI Seq 11011 TI value after Step 5 = 71
 Step 5 MI Seq 00100 MI for Step 5 = 20
 Step 6 TI Seq 110111 TI value after Step 6 = 107
 Step 6 MI Seq 001000 MI for Step 6 = 20
 Step 7 TI Seq 1101111 TI value after Step 7 = 161
 Step 7 MI Seq 0010000 MI for Step 7 = 84
 Step 8 TI Seq 11011111 TI value after Step 8 = 242
 Step 8 MI Seq 00100000 MI for Step 8 = 84
 Step 9 TI Seq 110111110 TI value after Step 9 = 121
 Step 9 MI Seq 001000001 MI for Step 9 = 84
 Step 10 TI Seq 1101111101 TI value after Step 10 = 182
 Step 10 MI Seq 0010000010 MI for Step 10 = 84
 Step 11 TI Seq 11011111010 TI value after Step 11 = 91
 Step 11 MI Seq 00100000101 MI for Step 11 = 84
 Step 12 TI Seq 110111110101 TI value after Step 12 = 137
 Step 12 MI Seq 001000001010 MI for Step 12 = 84
 Step 13 TI Seq 1101111101011 TI value after Step 13 = 206
 Step 13 MI Seq 0010000010100 MI for Step 13 = 4180
 Step 14 TI Seq 11011111010110 TI value after Step 14 = 103
 Step 14 MI Seq 00100000101001 MI for Step 14 = 12372
 Step 15 TI Seq 110111110101101 TI value after Step 15 = 155
 Step 15 MI Seq 001000001010010 MI for Step 15 = 12372

APPENDIX C. MISCELLANEOUS ITEMS

C.1. Background on Discovery of Proof. Discovery of the final proof came from a re-evaluation of the “interesting consequence” of Mirror Parity Sequences addressed in the preprint paper “Exactability versus Probability: Calming the Chaotic Collatz” [1] which was uploaded to Zenodo on 01 Feb 2025. Although none of the other references listed in this paper are directly referenced in this paper, they are referenced in the first paper and so are included here.

C.2. Outliers where $EV > EEV$ but $f^i(n_O) \not< n_O$. It has been proven that, at the first Step_i where $EV > EEV$, that $f^i(n_O) < n_O$. Although not needed for this proof, it will also be true for most n_O at all steps from 1 until $f^i(n_O) = 1$ that, if $EV > EEV$, then $f^i(n_O) < n_O$.

However, where $i_{plus} > i$, 593 Outliers were found, for $n_O \leq 4614$, that, although the n_O solved to $f^i(n_O) < n_O$ at Step_i , there are instances, in some cases multiple instances, where $f^{i_{plus}}(n_O) > n_O$ at a later $\text{Step}_{i_{plus}}$, although $EV > EEV$ at $\text{Step}_{i_{plus}}$. Outliers are distributed at steps 8, 27, 46, 54, 65, 73 and 93 as follows:

- 5 at Steps
- 50 at Step_{27} (8 + 19)
- 231 at Step_{46} (27 + 19)
- 2 at Step_{54} (46 + 8)
- 244 at Step_{65} (54 + 11)
- 56 at Step_{73} (65 + 8)
- 5 at Step_{92} (73 + 19)
 - Outliers at Step_{92} are: (3567, 4491, 4513, 4521 and 4551)

The first outlier occurs at $n_O = 7$, which initially solves to $f^7(7) = 5$ ($5 < 7$) at Step₇ with an $EV = .75 > EEV$ but solves to $f^8(7) = 8$ ($8 > 7$) at Step₈ although it still has an $EV = .6 > EEV$.

The last outlier occurs at $n_O = 4614$, which initially solves to $f^1(4614) = 2307$ ($2307 < 4614$) at Step₁ with an $EV = \text{Undefined} \ggg EEV$ but solves to $f^{73}(4614) = 4616$ ($4616 > 4614$) at Step₇₃ although it still has an $EV \approx 0.58695652173913 > EEV$.

All of the 593 outliers again reach $f^i(n_O) < n_O$ at a future step.

If, at Step _{i} , the value of $|w|$, where w is negative, is close enough to 0 then where:

$$EV_{i_{plus-i}} = \frac{q_{i_{plus}} - q_i}{p_{i_{plus}} - p_i}$$

if:

$$EV_{i_{plus-i}} \not> EEV$$

then at a future Step _{i_{plus}} , there is a possibility that:

$$f^{i_{plus}}(n_O) > f^i(n_O)$$

and therefore a possibility that:

$$f^{i_{plus}}(n_O) > n_O$$

although:

$$EV_{i_{plus}} > EEV$$

Since the lowest possible values of $|w|$ after the first time $EV > EEV$ increase as n_O increases, there is a point at which this possibility should no longer exist. If another unidentified outlier did exist, it would not invalidate this proof of the Collatz Conjecture.

C.3. Availability of Programming Scripts. Many of the R Scripts used while analyzing the conjecture are available and can be provided to peer reviewers or others interested.

C.4. Contacting the Author. I am willing to discuss this paper with anyone who has interest. Please contact me by email at Kenneth_Hutchings@yahoo.com with the word COLLATZ included in the subject line or by regular postal mail at 9734 Alister Drive, Melbourne FL 32940.

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9734 ALISTER DR., MELBOURNE, FL 32940
 Email address: Kenneth.Hutchings@yahoo.com